

Development and application of an eDNA-based sampling and analytic approach for integrated surveillance of wildlife-related pathogens

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Abstract

Recent emerging priorities in wildlife disease surveillance have created the need for integrated monitoring approaches across Europe. These methodologies, which merge passive and active surveillance with population monitoring, are essential for enhancing early pathogen detection, evaluating epidemiological dynamics, and assessing the progress or results of disease management interventions. This scientific report focuses on the use of eDNA in light of the need for integrated wildlife health monitoring. This study aims to test several hypotheses to further these goals: firstly, test if camera trap data can effectively inform the selection of sampling sites; secondly, the effectiveness of combining metabarcoding with metagenomic approaches for pathogen surveillance; and thirdly, the development of a harmonized strategy for selecting sampling sites to optimize sensitivity. Using as pilot areas three study sites monitored within the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife we had the opportunity of confronting three areas similar in terms of biodiversity (i.e. number of vertebrate species detectable by camera traps), all within the southern and western bioregions of Europe. In these three study areas wildlife trapping rates were coupled with topo-hydrographic data to identify suitable areas for environmental sampling characterized by high and low presence of animals respectively. Water and soil were used as environmental matrices. eDNA extracted from collected samples was analysed in parallel using metabarcoding and native sequencing (i.e., PCR-free metagenomic sequencing using nanopore technology). The obtained results confirmed the optimal

complementarity of both sample matrices and sequencing methodology which greatly contributed to increase detected biodiversity, both for mammals as well as for arthropod vectors and wildlife-related pathogens. The strategy for sampling site selection combining topographic and wildlife trapping rate showed no significant difference in terrestrial biodiversity (considering only mammals and birds which are likely to be detected by camera trapping). The possibility of improving species detection (and thus of related pathogens) is suggested when considering only sampling sites close to known areas of high occupancy (Camera traps with high trapping rate). While both methods provide valuable insights, they detect overlapping but distinct subsets of the community, highlighting the importance of integrating multiple approaches for biodiversity assessments. This pilot study marks a significant advancement in the standardization of eDNA methods, contributing to more effective wildlife surveillance systems. The integration of eDNA-based approaches with prior knowledge of the hydrographic features and watersheds of the study areas, together with prior knowledge of wildlife presence and abundance gives significant guidance to further pursue this line of research to integrate eDNA in wildlife health surveillance.

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Key words: environment, biodiversity, metabarcoding, metagenomic, diseases, wildlife

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Summary

Recent advancements in wildlife disease surveillance in Europe have underscored the necessity for integrated monitoring approaches that combine both passive and active surveillance techniques with population monitoring. The advent of eDNA analysis a decade ago revolutionized biodiversity research, shifting from single-species population dynamics to the detection of broader biodiversity, including cryptic and invasive species. This shift has not only enriched ecological and biodiversity sciences but also expanded eDNA's utility into health-related research fields such as disease surveillance and environmental contamination assessment. This report focuses on the application of environmental DNA (eDNA) as a tool to be potentially developed for integrated wildlife health monitoring. The study tests three main hypotheses: first, the effectiveness of using camera trap data to inform sampling site selection; second, the utility of integrating metabarcoding with metagenomic approaches for enhanced pathogen surveillance; and third, the development of a standardized strategy for selecting sampling sites to optimize the detection sensitivity.

The pilot study conducted as part of this report utilized camera traps in three European study areas to collect wildlife occurrence data, which, combined with topo-hydrographic data, informed the selection of sampling sites for eDNA collection from water and soil matrices. The parallel use of metabarcoding and metagenomic analysis on these samples provided a comprehensive picture of the biodiversity present, encompassing mammals, arthropod vectors, and DNA-based wildlife-related pathogens. The key findings of this report are:

Complementarity of eDNA and Camera Trapping: The integration of eDNA with camera trapping data showed that while both methods detected overlapping community subsets, each also highlighted unique elements of the biodiversity present. This underscores the importance of using multiple biodiversity assessment techniques to capture a complete ecological picture.

Efficiency of Metabarcoding and Metagenomics: Metabarcoding proved more sensitive in identifying vertebrate biodiversity and showed the importance of selecting appropriate markers for biodiversity assessments. Metagenomics, while offering broader taxonomic detection, requires post-hoc targeted assessment.

Biodiversity Insights: The study highlighted significant detections such as the presence of invasive species like the American mink. This points to the critical role of eDNA in providing early warnings for ecological and health surveillance.

Human and Domestic Animal DNA Detection: The detection of human and domestic animal DNA was recurrent, illustrating eDNA's capability to reflect anthropogenic impacts on ecosystems. This detection is crucial for understanding human and domestic animal interactions with wildlife and their potential role in disease transmission.

Pathogen Surveillance: The detection of vector-borne and directly transmissible pathogens via environmental sampling is highlighted. This indicates the potential of eDNA-based methods in early pathogen detection and monitoring disease outbreaks, particularly in areas free of disease. Passive (untargeted) pathogens' surveillance via native sequencing holds a very high potential for development.

This report concludes that while eDNA methodologies offer substantial benefits for wildlife health monitoring, they require further standardization and integration into systematic

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surveillance frameworks to fully capitalize on their potential. The study's findings contribute significantly to the ongoing development of integrated monitoring strategies, enhancing our capability to manage wildlife diseases effectively. The future of wildlife disease surveillance will likely see an increased reliance on these technologies, driven by their ability to provide comprehensive and timely data crucial for managing public health and biodiversity conservation.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, wildlife disease surveillance concepts and applicatives have evolved. In Europe, efforts have traditionally relied on passive surveillance methods and on targeted active pathogens' monitoring. The need for a more effective approach to surveillance of wildlife pathogens, has led to the proposal of integrating wildlife monitoring (IWM). IWMS combine passive (scanning or general) and active (targeted) disease surveillance with wildlife population monitoring (Cardoso et al., 2022). Surveillance and monitoring programs which actively incorporate wildlife population data, with scanning and targeted pathogen surveillance are essential to improve early detection of pathogens, assess epidemiological dynamics, freedom of disease, and the outcome of interventions (Barroso et al., 2023; Enetwild Consortium et al., 2023).

The European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as part of the ENETWILD project funded by EFSA, plays a crucial role in population monitoring. Through a collaborative network, standardized protocols have been developed and implemented to obtain harmonized data on the distribution and density of target mammal species. This "observatory" approach and the harmonized density estimates generated on a continental scale serve as a valuable foundation for the future development and harmonization of integrated monitoring programs, incorporating both host community and pathogen data (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024).

The environment, with its biotic and abiotic components, can provide a unifying framework for such integrated monitoring programs. Environmental DNA (eDNA) methods offer the potential to capture data on pathogens (e.g., invasive parasites, emerging or re-emerging viral or bacterial pathogens) and host communities (i.e., invasive or alien species, hosts involved in the parasite's life cycle or susceptible hosts) at a much earlier stage compared to traditional surveillance methods (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2023). These eDNA-based approaches, which allow researchers to detect species presence without the need for direct observation or capture, are increasingly used for pathogen detection, investigation, and surveillance (Bass et al., 2023). Environmental pathogen detection via eDNA methods could thus become a key component of One Health-integrated wildlife surveillance, primarily aimed at early pathogen detection (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022; Varzandi et al., 2025). Recently, the HaDEA One Health Surveillance Grant funded by the EU Commission, includes 7 targeted priority pathogens whose surveillance is also carried out via environmental sampling.

Environmental DNA has been used since the last two decades to address applied and fundamental research questions in ecology and molecular biology, initially with a special focus on monitoring biodiversity in fresh-water ecosystems, to expand to terrestrial and marine environments (Thomsen & Willerslev, 2015). eDNA methods, which analyse genetic material from water, soil, or air samples, offer numerous advantages that have transformed ecological research and conservation efforts. Compared to conventional techniques applied in biodiversity monitoring such as trapping, netting, or visual surveys, eDNA analysis is faster, more efficient, and non-invasive to organisms and their habitats. It also has high detection capabilities, holds promise for early warning systems aiming at detection of invasive species or emerging pathogens, and enables broad taxonomic assessments (Antognazza et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2019; Sawaya et al., 2019; Takahara et al., 2020; Yamanaka & Minamoto, 2016). Given the versatility of eDNA methods across different sampling and molecular detection stages, standardizing protocols at various levels is crucial for conducting large-scale studies.

Most eDNA studies to date have focused on water samples, with metabarcoding being the most commonly used multi-target analytical approach (Deiner et al., 2017; Ruppert et al.,

2019). In the context of One Health-integrated wildlife monitoring, PCR-free methods—such as native sequencing using nanopore technology via metagenomic or metatranscriptomic approaches—are particularly relevant and complementary to metabarcoding. These methods have the potential to identify a broader range of taxa, including pathogens and their hosts (both novel and existing), as well as invasive, threatened, endangered, or ecologically significant species, such as game species of interest to conservationists and wildlife managers (Bass et al., 2023). This is especially important for detecting parasitic diseases, where multiple host types, diverse parasitic forms, and complex environmental interactions complicate disease pathobiology. The same is true for multi-host pathogens with complex inter-specific epidemiological connections between reservoir hosts, and spill-over domestic or wild species. While these methods significantly enhance the scope of taxa detection, further optimization is needed to increase sequencing depth and improve the detection of low-abundance taxa.

Despite their potential, eDNA methods in wildlife surveillance require greater standardization in sampling and processing techniques. Currently, eDNA studies often rely on ad-hoc sampling site selection based on species distribution data (e.g., detecting trematodes by targeting habitats with pond snails (Varzandi et al., 2024). A methodologically sound field sampling is the foundation for subsequent analyses (Dickie et al., 2018; Theroux et al., 2025). Future approaches should reduce dependence on species distribution data, instead prioritizing sample collection strategies that capture eDNA representing the broadest possible biodiversity. This would enhance downstream detection probabilities for both hosts and pathogens (Carraro et al., 2021). Since eDNA transport dynamics are a key factor influencing detection success, sampling strategies should be designed to maximize the likelihood of encountering target eDNA. This can be achieved by selecting sampling sites that maximize biodiversity representation within a given study area (Barnes & Turner, 2016), which is particularly important for large-scale, harmonized monitoring programs.

Selecting sampling points based on surface water dynamics and elevation maps has proven effective for detecting landscape-scale mammalian fauna. While eDNA sampling of water bodies has been most successful for aquatic microorganisms (Cordier et al., 2017), detecting terrestrial vertebrates via stream water is possible with sensitive eDNA protocols, increased sampling replicates, and larger filtered water volumes (Lyet et al., 2021). Combining water samples with superficial soil—an important eDNA reservoir in terrestrial ecosystems—could further enhance biodiversity detection, capturing a more comprehensive genetic snapshot of the ecosystem. To address the objectives outlined in the Terms of Reference, this pilot study tests three key hypotheses related to wildlife surveillance using eDNA. The first hypothesis to be examined is whether occurrence data from direct observation via camera traps (WTR and LTR) can serve as effective priors for selecting sampling sites. This will involve analyzing the relevance and utility of camera trap data in enhancing site selection processes for further environmental sampling. The second hypothesis explores the efficacy of integrating metabarcoding with metagenomic approaches for the surveillance of wildlife-related pathogens. By testing these combined methodologies, the study aims to assess their performance in detecting pathogens more comprehensively. Lastly, the study aims at contributing toward the development of a harmonized and replicable strategy to identify sampling sites that maximize sensitivity in light of future use in systematic surveillance.

1.1 Terms of reference as provided by the requestor

Field trial to develop a protocol for the use of environmental DNA to set up a system for pathogen detection in the environment within a surveillance/monitoring system.

1.2 Aim of the report

This report aims at applying eDNA detection methods in study areas with known abundance of key-mammalian species established via harmonized camera-trapping methods. A standardized approach has been developed to identify sampling points based on camera trap detection rate, hydrological watersheds and water flow paths.

2 Data and Methodologies

2.1 Definition of study areas

Within the sites monitored in the framework of the European Observatory for Wildlife, three areas were chosen as pilot areas, namely: Prolom (Croatia), Quintos de Mora (Spain) and Santulhão (Portugal) (Fig. 1 and Tab. 1). The three areas are hunting grounds, covering an area ranging from 3000 to 7700 ha. The three locations belong to the continental-Mediterranean bio-region and have different levels of anthropization as well as presence (and abundance) of wild and domestic species.

Figure 1: Location and boundaries of the study areas.

The study sites, from west to east, are:

- Site 1: Prolom (UTM WGS84 4799319.115; 2474795.795)
- Site 2: Quintos de Mora (UTM WGS84 3107856.05; 1924580.56)
- Site 3: Santulhão (UTM WGS84 2939732.816; 2204913.369)

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ID	1	2	3
Study Site	Prolom	Quinto de Mora	Santulhão
Country	Croatia	Spain	Portugal
Bioregion	West	Southern	Southern
Institution	Univ. Zagreb	IREC- Universidad Castilla la Mancha	Palombar - Associação de Conservação da Natureza e do Património Rural
Area Type	Hunting ground	Hunting ground	Hunting ground
Area (ha)	7700	6700	2998
Habitat description	Mixed broad-leaved forest (~ 60 %) with grasslands (~10 %) and shrubs (~30%)	Mediterranean forest and shrublands, mainly Pine reforestation and Quercus with scattered cereal crops	Mainly shrubland (ca. 50%) interspersed with agricultural fields (~32%), pastures (~2%) and broadleaved and coniferous forests (~16%). Surface water bodies also present (~1%)
Big vertebrates present	<i>Sus scrofa</i> , <i>Cervus elaphus</i> , <i>Capreolus capreolus</i> , <i>Dama dama</i> , <i>Canis lupus</i> . (n=5)	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i> , <i>C. capreolus</i> , <i>D. dama</i> (n=4)	<i>Sus scrofa</i> and <i>Capreolus capreolus</i> were detected by camera traps. <i>Cervus elaphus</i> and <i>Canis lupus signatus</i> are known to be present in the area based on other sources, but were not detected by direct observation. (n=4)

Small vertebrates present	<i>V. vulpes</i> , <i>M. meles</i> , <i>F. silvestris</i> , <i>C. aureus</i> , <i>C. fiber</i> , <i>M. foina</i> , <i>M. martes</i> , <i>Mustela putorius</i> , <i>L. europaeus</i> , <i>L. lutra</i> , <i>E. europaeus</i> , <i>S. vulgaris</i> , <i>G. glis</i> (n=13)	<i>V. vulpes</i> , <i>Martes foina</i> , <i>Lepus granatensis</i> , <i>Genetta genetta</i> , <i>Herpestes ichneumon</i> , <i>Lynx pardinus</i> (n=6)	<i>V. vulpes</i> , <i>M. meles</i> , <i>M. foina</i> , <i>G. genetta</i> , <i>L. granatensis</i> , <i>O. cuniculus</i> , <i>A. sylvaticus</i> , <i>H. ichneumon</i> , <i>E. europaeus</i> , <i>C. russula</i> , <i>M. cabreranae</i> , <i>M. lusitanicus</i> , <i>L. lutra</i> were not detected by direct observation but their presence was confirmed by other sources. (n=13)
Livestock species	Cattle, horses, sheep, goats, pigs	None	Cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, equines
Other domestic animals present	Dog	NA	Dogs, cats
Livestock grazing	Yes	No	Yes
Artificial feeding	Yes	No	No
Fencing	No	Yes	No
Cameras deployed	17/07/24	13/09/2024	25/06/2024
Cameras removed	20/11/24	29/11/2024	10/10/2024
Wild boar density (95% se)	23.61 (se 5.77; cv 0.24)	4.05 (se 1.62; cv 0.39)	3.61 (se 1.52; cv 0.42)
Roe deer density (95% se)	5.94 (se 1.13; cv 0.19)	9.57 (se 2.2, cv 0.23)	6.20 (se 1.85; cv 0.30)

Commented [1]: The same here. It is important to differentiate what species were detected by camera trapping from those that weren't (please check again the shared Excel file with this information).

Red deer density (95% se)	1.11 (se 0.82; cv 0.74)	4.36 (se 2.95, cv 0.67)	na
Red Fox density (95% se)	1.03 (se 0.35; cv 0.34)	47.22 (se 9.4;cv 0.2)	1.07 (se 0.46; cv 0.43)
Badger density (95% se)	0.85 (se 0.42; cv 0.49)	1.01 (se 0.26,cv 0.26)	na
Stone marten density (95% se)	0.38 (se 0.18; cv 0.48)	0.10 (se 0.06,cv 0.61)	na
Fallow deer (95% se)	na	0.56 (se 0.34,cv 0.59)	na

Table 1. A summary description of key factors of the three study areas, including animal species present, management type and density values estimated via Random Encounter Model within the European Observatory for wildlife (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024).

2.1.1 Study area 1: Prolom

Prolom is a nature reserve located in central Croatia, Sisak-Moslavina County, directly on the state border with Bosnia and Herzegovina. It covers the westernmost slopes and parts of the Zrinska Gora massif and takes its name from the Prolom forest complex. The study area is mountainous, most of which is covered with forest vegetation. The entire study area slopes downwards towards the north, with the lowest altitude of 170 m, where the belt of climatic hornbeam *Carpinus betulus* forests predominates. The highest peak in the southern part is 529 m asl, where the belt of acidophilous beech *Fagus sylvatica* forests and Illyrian beech (*F. sylvatica*) forests predominates. The water areas include streams that favour wildlife habitat and retention. The remaining territory consists of non-forested areas, namely neglected farmland, meadows and pastures. According to Köppen classification, this area belongs to "Cfbw" climate, that means a warm and rainy climate with frost and snow in the (cold) winter part of the year (Zaninović et al., 2008). The annual rainfall is around 1079 mm.

The study area is inhabited by wild boar *Sus scrofa* in the highest densities, together with other ungulate species, namely: roe deer *Capreolus capreolus*, fallow deer *Dama dama* and red deer *Cervus elaphus* (see Table 2 for density estimations). Density estimation in the study area is carried out continuously by camera traps and Random Encounter Model "REM" (Rowcliffe et al. 2008). Large carnivores are also present, i.e. the grey wolf *Canis lupus* and occasionally the brown bear *Ursus arctos*.

2.1.2 Study area 2 : Quintos de Mora

Quintos de Mora, (Toledo) is a government-owned and operated park spanning 6,864 hectares in Central Spain (39°25'N, 4°04'W). The park features a diverse range of habitats and is divided into two main sections: a plain situated at 800 meters above sea level, traversed by the Navas River, and a mountainous area reaching up to 1,235 meters above sea level. It experiences a Mediterranean climate with a dry season from June to September (average rainfall approximately 14 mm; average temperature around 24°C) and a wet season that sees most rainfall during the winter and spring (average rainfall approximately 33 mm; average temperature around 10°C). The vegetation is varied, with an upper layer dominated by *Pinus pinea*, *P. pinaster*, *Quercus rotundifolia*, and *Q. faginea*, and a shrub-based understory that includes *Arbutus unedo*, *Phillyrea angustifolia*, *Cistus ladanifer*, and *Erica* spp., all at different stages of succession. The most representative mammals are the hunting species red deer, wild boar (*S. scrofa*), fallow deer (*D. dama*), and roe deer (*C. capreolus*). Livestock has not been present in Quintos de Mora for at least five decades.

2.1.3 Study area 3: Santulhão

Santulhão is an associative hunting Area managed by a local hunting association (Associação de Caçadores de Santulhão), which collaborates with Palombar on several projects related to biodiversity monitoring. It is located in northeastern Portugal, in the Trás-os-Montes region and it is characterized by a diverse assemblage of habitats that support a variety of faunal species. The dominant vegetation type is shrubland, comprising approximately 50% of the area. This is interspersed with agricultural fields, which occupy about 32% of the landscape. Pastures are relatively sparse, covering only 2% of the terrain. The forested regions, encompassing both broadleaved and coniferous species, constitute

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approximately 16% of the land cover. Additionally, minor surface water bodies, accounting for about 1% of the area.

The principal wildlife species inhabiting Santulhão include wild boar (*S. scrofa*), roe deer (*C. capreolus*), red deer (*C. elaphus*), and Iberian wolf (*Canis lupus signatus*). These species are indicative of the region's rich biodiversity and its importance for conservation and management studies. The integration of various land uses within Santulhão supports a complex ecological network that is crucial for the sustainability of these populations, thereby underlining the area's significance for biological and ecological research in addition to its use as a hunting reserve.

2.2 Overview of available epidemiological data for each study area

For the three selected study areas epidemiological data are available for a varied range of pathogens whose life cycle is related to wild animal species and for which a relevant environmental phase exists. The most recent epidemiological studies carried out in the three areas are reported in the table below.

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Area	Target pathogen(s)	Epidemiologically relevant wildlife	Epidemiologically relevant livestock	Environmental phase	Target animal population	Matrix	Reported epidemiological value	Diagnostic method	Reference
1	Trypanosoma pestanaei, Hemotropic mycoplasmas, Ehrlichia spp, Babesia sp	<i>Meles meles</i>	Cattle, sheep	Ixodidae ticks (eggs, and questing stages); Flea (<i>Paraceras melis</i>)	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Blood, spleen	T. pestanaei 68%; Hemotropic Mycoplasma spp. 45%	PCR, Sanger sequencing	Lindhorst, Z.T.L. et al. (2024). Molecular analysis of vector-borne pathogens in Eurasian badgers (<i>Meles meles</i>) from continental Europe. <i>Parasites & Vectors</i> , 17: 451. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-024-06515-y
1	Eimeria sp., Strongyloides sp.; Strongyle nematodes	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Cattle, sheep	Oocysts and (larvated) eggs respectively	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Feaces	Not stated	Semi-quantitative and sedimentation methods	Oleinic, R. et al. (2024). Testing the 'parasite-mediated domestication' hypothesis: a comparative approach to the wild boar and domestic pig as model species. <i>PeerJ</i> , 12:e18463. https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.18463
1	Hepatozoon spp	<i>Rupicapra rupicapra</i> , <i>Ovis musimon</i> , <i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. capreolus</i> , <i>Canis aureus</i> , <i>C. lupus</i> , <i>U. arctos</i> , <i>M. meles</i> , <i>Martes foina</i> , <i>Erinaceus europaeus</i> , <i>Lepus europaeus</i> , <i>M. glareus</i> , <i>Apodemus flavicollis</i> , <i>A. sylvaticus</i>	Cattle, sheep	Ixodidae ticks	Artiodactyla, Carnivora	Spleen	80.8% in Golden Jackal, 54.2% in Wolf, 9.4% in Badger, 63.6% in Stone marten, 100% in Hedgehog, 0.6% in European brown Hare, 81.8 in Bank vole, 8.1% in Yellow neck mouse, 14.6% in Wood mouse	PCR, 18S rRNA ribosomal DNA sequencing	Uiterwijk, M. et al. (2023). Diversity of Hepatozoon species in wild mammals and ticks in Europe. <i>Parasites & Vectors</i> , 16: 27. doi: 10.1186/s13071-022-05626-8

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1	Gastrointestinal helminth, protozoan parasites	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	Cattle, sheep	<i>F. silvestris</i>	Gastrointestinal tract, faeces, diaphragm	Taenia taeniaeformis (55.9%), Capillaria sp. (50%), Toxocara cati (50%), Isospora sp. (29.4%), Strongyloides sp. (23.5%), Giardia sp. (17.6%), Ancylostoma tubaeformae (14.7%), Physaloptera sp. (11.8%), Hymenolepididae (8.8%), Alaria alata (5.9%), Aelurostrongylus abstrusus (5.9%), Toxascaris leonina (5.9%), Mesocestoides lineatus (5.9%), Anoplocephalidae (2.9%), Dipylidium caninum (2.9%), Trichuris sp. (2.9%), Isospora felis (2.9%), Eimeria sp. (2.9%) and Sarcocystis sp. (2.9%)	Copromicroscopy and morphological identification of macroscopic specimens	Martinković, F. et al. (2017). Endoparasites of wildcats in Croatia. Veterinarski arhiv, 87: 713- 729. https://doi.org/10.24099/vet.arhiv.170127
3	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex			<i>S. scrofa</i>	Submandibular; tracheobronchial, and mesenteric		Gross pathology	Cardoso, B. et al. (2024) Performance of post-mortem diagnostic tests for tuberculosis in wild ungulates at low and high prevalence assessed using Bayesian latent class models. Front. Vet. Sci. 11:1415277. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2024.1415277
3	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex			<i>S. scrofa</i>	Pooled lymph nodes (submandibular; tracheobronchial; and		IS6110 Real-time PCR	Cardoso, B. et al. (2024) Performance of post-mortem diagnostic tests for tuberculosis in wild ungulates at low and high prevalence assessed using Bayesian latent class models. Front. Vet. Sci. 11:1415277. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2024.1415277

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				mesenteric)			
3	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex		<i>S. scrofa</i>	Pooled lymph nodes (submandibular; tracheobronchial; and mesenteric)	0.85 (<0.001–6.30)	Bacteriological culture	Cardoso, B. et al. (2024) Performance of post-mortem diagnostic tests for tuberculosis in wild ungulates at low and high prevalence assessed using Bayesian latent class models. <i>Front. Vet. Sci.</i> 11:1415277. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2024.1415277
3	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex		<i>S. scrofa</i>	Blood		P22 ELISA	Cardoso, B. et al. (2024) Performance of post-mortem diagnostic tests for tuberculosis in wild ungulates at low and high prevalence assessed using Bayesian latent class models. <i>Front. Vet. Sci.</i> 11:1415277. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2024.1415277
3	Mixoma virus	<i>O. cuniculus</i> , <i>L. granatensis</i>	Infected fomites, arthropod vectors	<i>O. cuniculus</i>	Blood	(Ingezim 17.MIX.K1, Eurofins Technologies Ingenasa, Spain)	Ferreira-e-Silva J, et al., (2025) Evaluation of dried blood spots for serological surveys of myxoma and rabbit hemorrhagic disease viruses in their wild reservoir. <i>Prev. Vet. Med.</i> 234: 106369. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2024.106369
3	Rabbit Hemorrhagic Disease Virus	<i>O. cuniculus</i> , <i>L. granatensis</i>	Infected fomites, arthropod vectors	<i>O. cuniculus</i>	Blood	in-house iELISA	Ferreira-e-Silva J, et al., (2025) Evaluation of dried blood spots for serological surveys of myxoma and rabbit hemorrhagic disease viruses in their wild reservoir. <i>Prev. Vet. Med.</i> 234: 106369. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2024.106369

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2	Toxoplasma gondii, Neospora caninum	All warm-blooded species as intermediate hosts, <i>F. silvestris</i> as definitive hosts	All warm-blooded species	Oocysts	<i>C. capreolus</i>	Blood serum	13% <i>T. gondii</i> ; 2% <i>N. caninum</i>		San Miguel J.M. et al., (2016). Effect of different ecosystems and management practices on <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> and <i>Neospora caninum</i> infections in wild ruminants in Spain. <i>J Wildl Dis.</i> 52 (2): 293–300. doi: https://doi.org/10.7589/2015-07-176
2	<i>Mycobacterium bovis</i>	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	Infected fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Organs	85% prevalence	Gross pathology and Mycobacterial culture in parallel	Queirós, J. . et al. (2018). Genome-wide associations identify novel candidate loci associated with genetic susceptibility to tuberculosis in wild boar. <i>Sci Rep</i> 8, 1980. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-20158-x	
2	<i>Hypoderma actaeon</i>	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Thrid in-star larvae and pupae	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Sub-cutaneous tissues	The prevalence of warbles was 44.8% and the intensity of infection was 38.29 (SD ± 61.32) warbles/deer infected	Gross pathology	Fuente-López, C.D.L., et al., (2001), Seasonal changes in prevalence and intensity of <i>Hypoderma actaeon</i> in <i>Cervus elaphus</i> from central Spain. <i>Medical and Veterinary Entomology</i> , 15: 204-207. https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2915.2001.00287.x	
2	<i>Spiculopteria asymmetrica</i> / <i>S. quadrispiculata</i> , <i>Ostertagia leptospicularis</i> / <i>O. kolchida</i> , <i>O. drozdzi</i> / <i>O. ryjikovi</i> and <i>Trichostrongylus axei</i>	<i>C. elephas</i> , <i>C. capreolus</i> , <i>D. dama</i> , <i>O. musimon</i>	Eggs and third in-star larvae	<i>C. elaphus</i> , <i>D. dama</i>	Abomasum	<i>Spiculopteria asymmetrica</i> / <i>S. quadrispiculata</i> 96.3%, <i>Ostertagia leptospicularis</i> / <i>O. kolchida</i> 67.9%, <i>O. drozdzi</i> / <i>O. ryjikovi</i> 33.3% and <i>Trichostrongylus axei</i> 2.47%	Morphological identification of Adult nematodes	Santín-Durán, M. et al., (2008). Age Distribution and Seasonal Dynamics of Abomasal Helminths in Wild Red Deer from Central Spain. <i>J. Parasitol.</i> 94: 1031–1037.	
2	<i>Brucella</i> spp.	<i>C. elephas</i> , <i>C. capreolus</i> , <i>D. dama</i> , <i>O. musimon</i>	Infected fomites	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Blood serum	Prevalence 0.00%	Rose bengal test	San-Miguel Ayanz J.M., et al., (2017). Seroprevalence of Leptospirosis, Brucellosis, and Q Fever in a Wild Red Deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>) Population Kept in a Fenced Reserve in Absence of Contact with Livestock. <i>Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases</i> , 17: 10. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2016.2105	
2	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>	<i>C. elaphus</i>	infected fomites and infected Ixodidae ticks	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Blood serum	Prevalence 0.00%	LSIVet™ Ruminant Q Fever (LSI, Lissieu, France)	San-Miguel Ayanz J.M., et al., 2017. Seroprevalence of Leptospirosis, Brucellosis, and Q Fever in a Wild Red Deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>) Population Kept in a Fenced Reserve in Absence of	

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							Contact with Livestock. Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases, 17: 10. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2016.2105	
2	Leptospira spp	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Infected fomites	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Blood serum	Prevalence 38.5% (97/252; 95% CI: 32.9-44.0), serovar Pomona	Microagglutination Laboratorio Central de Veterinaria" (Algete, Madrid, Spain), PCR on MAT positive samples	San-Miguel Ayanz J.M., et al., 2017. Seroprevalence of Leptospirosis, Brucellosis, and Q Fever in a Wild Red Deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>) Population Kept in a Fenced Reserve in Absence of Contact with Livestock. Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases, 17: 10. https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2016.2105
2	Aujeszky disease virus	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Infected fomites and carcasses	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Blood serum	56.3% (CI95% 45,3-66,9)		e Melo, N.M. Abreu de,Roboredo Sampaio. Estudo da prevalência de excreção com a variação do nível de seroprevalência da doença de aujeszky em populações de javalis na península ibérica. [Order No. 30650081]. Universidade de Tras-os-Montes e Alto Douro (Portugal); 2016.
2	Aujeszky disease virus	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Infected fomites and carcasses	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Lymphoid tissue (tonsil) and nervous tissue, oral, nasal and genital swabs	Prevalence in nervous system 5.3% (CI95% 0.1 - 26.0); total excretion in fomites 5.9% (CI95% 0.2 - 28.7)	in-house iELISA	e Melo, N.M. Abreu de,Roboredo Sampaio. Estudo da prevalência de excreção com a variação do nível de seroprevalência da doença de aujeszky em populações de javalis na península ibérica. [Order No. 30650081]. Universidade de Tras-os-Montes e Alto Douro (Portugal); 2016.
2	Pharyngomyia picta and Cephemyia auribarbis	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Thrid in-star larvae and pupae	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Pharynge and lungs	Prevalence was 50.6 ± 7.61%	Gross pathology	de la Fuente C, San Miguel JM, Santin M, Alunda JM, Domínguez I, López A, Carballo M, González A. Pharyngeal bot flies in <i>Cervus elaphus</i> in central Spain: prevalence and population dynamics. J Parasitol. 2000 Feb;86(1):33-7. doi: 10.1645/0022-3395(2000)086[0033:PBFACE]2.0.CO;2. PMID: 10701560.
2	Sarcocystis. Hjorti, S. linearis, S. cervicanis, S.	<i>C. elaphus, carnivores</i>	Carnivore feces, infected fomites	<i>C. elaphus, carnivores</i>	diaphragm and heart	97%	Microscopic compression	Gjerde, B., Luzón, M., Alunda, J.M. et al. Morphological and molecular characteristics of six <i>Sarcocystis</i> spp. from red deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>) in Spain,

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								method and PCR	including <i>Sarcocystis cervicanis</i> and three new species. <i>Parasitol Res</i> 116, 2795–2811 (2017). https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-017-5590-z
2	Onchocerca flexuosa	<i>C. elaphus</i>		Transmitted by simuliids	<i>C. elaphus</i>	ubcutaneous nodules	5-48%	Gross pathology	San-Miguel JM, Alvarez G, Rodríguez-Vigal C, Luzón M. Nodular onchocercosis of red deer in central Spain. <i>Vet Parasitol.</i> 2003 May 15;114(1):75-9. doi: 10.1016/s0304-4017(03)00097-9.
2	Brucella suis biovar 2	<i>S. scrofa</i>		fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Blood serum and spleen	25%	multi-species indirect enzyme immunoassay (IELISA), multiplex PCR and PCR-RFLP	Muñoz PM, Boadella M, Arnal M, de Miguel MJ, Revilla M, Martínez D, Vicente J, Acevedo P, Oleaga A, Ruiz-Fons F, Marín CM, Prieto JM, de la Fuente J, Barral M, Barberán M, de Luco DF, Blasco JM, Gortázar C. Spatial distribution and risk factors of Brucellosis in Iberian wild ungulates. <i>BMC Infect Dis.</i> 2010 Mar 5;10:46. doi: 10.1186/1471-2334-10-46. PMID: 20205703
2	Enterocytozoon bienersi	<i>C. elaphus</i> , <i>S. scrofa</i>	humans, animals, and birds	fomites	<i>C. elaphus</i> , <i>S. scrofa</i>	Feaces	red deer (10.4%, 68/653) and wild boar (0.8%, 3/359).	PCR	Dashti A, Santín M, Köster PC, Bailo B, Ortega S, Imaña E, Habela MÁ, Rivero-Juarez A, Vicente J; WE&H group; Arnal MC, de Luco DF, Morrondo P, Armenteros JA, Balseiro A, Cardona GA, Martínez-Carrasco C, Ortiz JA, Calero-Bernal R, Carmena D, González-Barrio D. Zoonotic Enterocytozoon bienersi genotypes in free-ranging and farmed wild ungulates in Spain. <i>Med Mycol.</i> 2022 Sep 30;60(9):myac070. doi: 10.1093/mmy/myac070.
2	Blastocystis	<i>S. scrofa</i>	humans, animals, and birds	fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Feaces	10%	PCR	öster PC, Figueiredo AM, Maloney JG, Dashti A, Bailo B, Torres RT, Fonseca C, Mysterud A, Habela MÁ, Rivero-Juarez A, Vicente J, Serrano E, Arnal MC, de Luco DF, Armenteros JA, Balseiro A, Cardona GA, Carvalho J, Hipólito D, Fernandes J, Palmeira JD, Calero-Bernal R, González-Barrio D, Santin M, Carmena D. Correction: Blastocystis occurrence and subtype diversity in European wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) from the Iberian Peninsula. <i>Vet Res.</i> 2024 Nov 14;55(1):152. doi:

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									10.1186/s13567-024-01408-5. Erratum for: Vet Res. 2024 Oct 7;55(1):133. doi: 10.1186/s13567-024-01385-9.
2	Cryptosporidium spp and Giardia duodenalis	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	Ungulates	fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	Faeces	Presence	PCR	Dashti A, Köster PC, Bailo B, de Las Matas AS, Habela MÁ, Rivero-Juarez A, Vicente J, Serrano E, Arnal MC, de Luco DF, Morrondo P, Armenteros JA, Balseiro A, Cardona GA, Martínez-Carrasco C, Ortiz JA, Carpio AJ, Calero-Bernal R, González-Barrio D, Carmena D. Occurrence and limited zoonotic potential of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp., <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> , and <i>Balantioides coli</i> infections in free-ranging and farmed wild ungulates in Spain. Res Vet Sci. 2023 Jun;159:189-197. doi: 10.1016/j.rvsc.2023.04.020.
2	BTV-4	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Cattle, sheep	Culicoides	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Blood	12.9	ELISA	Falconi C, López-Olvera JR, Boadella M, Camarena J, Rosell R, Alcaide V, Vicente J, Sánchez-Vizcaino JM, Pujols J, Gortázar C. Evidence for BTV-4 circulation in free-ranging red deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>) in Cabañeros National Park, Spain. Vet Microbiol. 2012 Sep 14;159(1-2):40-6. doi: 10.1016/j.vetmic.2012.03.023.
2	Schmallenberg	<i>C. elaphus</i>		Culicoides	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Blood	18.8	ELISA	Jiménez-Ruiz S, Riscalde MA, Acevedo P, Arnal MC, Gómez-Guillamón F, Prieto P, Gens MJ, Cano-Terriza D, Fernández de Luco D, Vicente J, García-Bocanegra I. Serosurveillance of Schmallenberg virus in wild ruminants in Spain. Transbound Emerg Dis. 2021 Mar;68(2):347-354.
2	Hepatitis E virus	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	Ungulates	fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	blood	10.12% (95% CI: 5.44-14.8) from wild boar , 16.05% samples (95% CI: 8.06-24.04) red deer	ELISA and real-time RT-PCR	Kukielka D, Rodríguez-Prieto V, Vicente J, Sánchez-Vizcaino JM. Constant Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) Circulation in Wild Boar and Red Deer in Spain: An Increasing Concern Source of HEV Zoonotic Transmission. Transbound Emerg Dis. 2016 Oct;63(5):e360-8. doi: 10.1111/tbed.12311. Boadella M, Casas M, Martín M, Vicente J, Segalés J, de la Fuente J, Gortázar C. Increasing contact with hepatitis E virus in red deer, Spain. Emerg Infect Dis. 2010

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Dec;16(12):1994-6. doi:
10.3201/eid1612.100557.

2	Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	Ungulates	fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i> , <i>C. elaphus</i>	lymph nodes and lung	30% wild boar, 10% red deer	Gross pathology and PCR	Vicente J, Barasona JA, Acevedo P, Ruiz-Fons JF, Boadella M, Díez-Delgado I, Beltrán-Beck B, González-Barrio D, Queirós J, Montoro V, de la Fuente J, Gortazar C. Temporal trend of tuberculosis in wild ungulates from Mediterranean Spain. <i>Transbound Emerg Dis.</i> 2013 Nov;60 Suppl 1:92-103. doi: 10.1111/tbed.12167.
2	Aujeszky disease virus	<i>S. scrofa</i>		Infected fomites and carcasses	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Lymphoid tissue (tonsil) and nervous tissue, oral, nasal and genital swabs	35%	in-house iELISA	Boadella M, Gortázar C, Vicente J, Ruiz-Fons F. Wild boar: an increasing concern for Aujeszky's disease control in pigs? <i>BMC Vet Res.</i> 2012 Jan 17;8:7. doi: 10.1186/1746-6148-8-7.
2	Trichinella spp	<i>S. scrofa</i>			<i>S. scrofa</i>		20%	ELISA	Boadella M, Barasona JA, Pozio E, Montoro V, Vicente J, Gortazar C, Acevedo P. Spatio-temporal trends and risk factors for Trichinella species infection in wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) populations of central Spain: a long-term study. <i>Int J Parasitol.</i> 2012 Jul;42(8):739-45. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpara.2012.05.003
2	Porcine circovirus 2	<i>S. scrofa</i>	Pig	Fomites	<i>S. scrofa</i>		75%	ELISA	Díez-Delgado I, Boadella M, Martín-Hernando M, Barasona JA, Beltrán-Beck B, González-Barrio D, Sibila M, Vicente J, Garrido JM, Segalés J, Gortazar C. Complex links between natural tuberculosis and porcine circovirus type 2 infection in wild boar. <i>Biomed Res Int.</i> 2014;2014:765715. doi: 10.1155/2014/765715
2	Anaplasma	<i>C. elaphus</i>		Ticks	<i>C. elaphus</i>	Serum and ticks	10%	ELISA, PCR	De La Fuente J, Vicente J, Höfle U, Ruiz-Fons F, Fernández De Mera IG, Van Den Bussche RA, Kocan KM, Gortazar C.

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Anaplasma infection in free-ranging Iberian red deer in the region of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain. *Vet Microbiol.* 2004 Jun 3;100(3-4):163-73. doi: 10.1016/j.vetmic.2004.02.007.

Table 2. Most recent epidemiological data available for the three study areas for wildlife-related pathogens.

2.3 Selection of sampling points

2.3.1 Predictor variables

A methodological approach was adopted to explore the enhancement of detection capabilities for wildlife and associated pathogens, within the framework of integrated one-health surveillance. Although commonly employed for biodiversity assessments, the application of eDNA has limited research focused on its durability and mobility, predominantly in aquatic environments (Ariza et al., 2023). Understanding these characteristics of eDNA is essential for the formulation of uniform protocols for disease surveillance initiatives. eDNA contains a complex mixture of nuclear and mitochondrial DNA, released by various organisms into their surroundings via bodily fluids, skin cells, and hair. This leads to eDNA samples consisting of both intact intracellular DNA and degraded extracellular DNA, often appearing as short fragments due to cellular breakdown and environmental degradation. eDNA includes DNA from whole organisms as well as from disintegrated tissues or unbound genetic material found in environmental samples such as water, soil, sediment, feces, or air. The genetic contributions from diverse species in these habitats are naturally processed through a hierarchical hydrological system. Consequently, sampling efforts focused on soil samples in correspondence of water run-off that form temporarily after rainfall and on water from lotic or lentic water bodies, with the goal of detecting variations in species concentrations to establish ideal sampling locations. These selected sites are studied to assess the relationship between fluctuations in species density and the detection of vertebrate DNA and pathogens. The determination of these locations and the selection of sampling points are guided by various predictive factors, listed below.

2.3.2 Wildlife abundance and distribution

The goal was to identify regions with high and low wildlife abundance while trying to minimize the presence of livestock. To estimate areas of higher and lower wildlife abundance, data from European Wildlife Observatory (EOW) were analysed for the late summer months of 2023 across the three study areas (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Camera trap network for each of the study areas

The calculation of the trapping rate was performed by translating the recorded captures of various species into a standardized format, adjusting for the number of active days of the camera traps to factor in the sampling effort. This metric serves as an index to estimate the relative abundance of species at each camera location. To achieve this, the total number of detections for each species was recorded and subsequently used to calculate a specific capture rate, expressed as detections per unit of effort. The species analyzed included wild boar, ruminant ungulates and carnivores. The same process was carried out for domestic animals (both livestock and dogs and cats).

To normalize the data across different study areas, allowing for an accurate comparison, the values obtained from each location were standardized. This normalization process ensures that the trapping rates are comparable despite potential variations in environmental conditions or sampling intensity across the study areas.

Furthermore, to spatially analyze and represent the abundance of wildlife and livestock as recorded by the camera traps, an Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method was utilized (QGIS Development Team, 2024). In this geospatial analysis technique, each sampled point is weighted inversely proportional to its distance from the location being estimated, effectively reducing the influence of distant observations on the estimate at any given point. This results in a smoother gradient of species abundance across the landscape. Following the application of IDW, the continuous interpolated values were then categorized based on a quantile approach. This method divides the range of data into equal-sized intervals, which were used for further selecting sampling points. The resulting raster layers wildlife trapping rate (WTR) and livestock trapping rate (LTR) are reported in figure 3 and 4 respectively.

Figure 3. Wildlife trapping rate: *trapping rate interpolation based on detection rates for wild mammals indicators*. Panel A Area 1 Prolom, Croatia, B Area 2 Quintos de Mora, Spain, C Santulhao, Portugal.

Figure 4. Trapping rate interpolation based on detection rates for livestock species. In area 2 (Quintos de Mora), no domestic animals/livestock is present. Panel A Area 1 Prolom, Croatia, B Santulhao, Portugal.

2.3.3 Topography and stream network

Due to dynamic hydrological processes, eDNA samples from running waters and underlying soil are assumed to represent biodiversity from broad contributing areas upstream. This assumption, which lies at the basis of biological use of eDNA, is convenient from a biomonitoring perspective but also challenging, as a-priori hydrological knowledge is required for meaningful biological interpretation (Urycki et al., 2024; Varzandi et al., 2024). For each study area, stream sub-basins and topographical data from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) were used as additional criteria for selecting sampling locations. The stream sub-basins, essential for defining the hydrological boundaries of watersheds, were sourced from the "EU-Hydro" River Network Database provided by the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, covering the period 2006–2012 in vector format (European Environment Agency, 2019). These delineations play a crucial role in determining distinct zones for investigating DNA dispersal mechanisms via surface runoff, as outlined by Urycki et al., in their 2024 study on genetic material transport dynamics.

In our efforts to assess the complexity of water stream networks within these areas, both ephemeral and perennial streams were identified using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM). This process was facilitated by the integration of the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) 30-meter resolution DEM available through NASA's Earth Data portal (nasa.gov) and Google Earth Engine. The network of watercourses was then calculated employing the ArcGeek Calculator, a Python-based plugin for the Geographic Information System (GIS) software QGIS (Pucha-Cofrep, 2024). This plugin enabled the application of the Strahler stream order method to classify the hierarchy of streams. Additionally, the High Resolution

Layer Water and Wetness dataset, part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) offerings, was instrumental in identifying discrete water bodies and regions of sustained or intermittent moisture in vector format.

To supplement these datasets (Figure 5), satellite images of each study area were meticulously analyzed to identify and mark smaller water bodies such as ponds, pools, and lagoons through detailed photo-interpretation techniques. Any direct knowledge from field-operators was also included. This multi-sourced approach gave a detailed understanding of the aquatic landscapes within the study areas for subsequent ecological assessments and sampling strategies.

Figure 5 Watershed and the corresponding draining water stream as derived from DEM analysis.

After interpolation of the topo-hydrographic layer with WTR and LTR, sampling points were selected as follows: i) Combining geographic information with WTR and LTR, proposed sampling points and areas that meet the established selection criteria; i) allocate sampling points evenly between areas of high and low actual wildlife abundance (WTR) for each study area, where points of high wildlife abundance were the top quartile of WTR, and areas of low abundance those with WTR values in the lowest quartile, ii) sampling points to be located preferably in correspondence of permanent water streams located in proximity of first order water points (thus draining one upstream watershed) or alternatively, permanent or semi-permanent lotic water points that allow for successful collection of water samples.

2.4 Sample collection

Considering the criteria mentioned above, ten sampling points were selected for each study area. These points were distributed nearly evenly across WTR and LTR areas, with the Croatian and Portuguese study areas having six points in WTR areas and Spain having five.

At each sampling point, one soil sample and two water sample replicates were collected using separate filters and filtering volumes, following the protocol described below.

2.4.1 Necessary equipment for sampling in the field

For each sampling point the following material is necessary:

- i. Two high-capacity filters (0.1 μm Waterra filters, Argaly, Sainte-Helene Du Lac, France), two 50 mL falcon tubes, DNA/RNA-free steel spoon for soil collection (Figure 6a).
- ii. Two 50 mL syringes, two Pasteur pipettes, and one 50 mL falcon (to be used for dispensing preservation buffer) (Figure 6b).
- iii. Personal Protection Equipment (to avoid contamination): disposable sterile gloves (in three different sizes for each sampling point) and masks (Figure 6.c).
- iv. AVL buffer: lysis and preservation buffer to be added into water and soil samples. To avoid buffer precipitation it is recommended to keep the solution at 15-25 ° C (Figure 6d).
- v. Transport containers: polystyrene box to store AVL buffer at stable temperature. If necessary, under cold field-conditions, use disposable hand-warmers provided to keep AVL buffer above 15°C (Figure 6e).
- vi. Pumping device: diaphragm pump (connected to a 12V battery).

Figure 6. Material necessary for sample collection in the field.

2.4.2 Sample collection

Locate sampling site via GPS coordinates, once at the designated site, survey the immediate surroundings for any sign of water runoff. Identify the origin of the runoff and assess whether it flows towards a lotic (such as a stream or river) or lentic (such as a pond) water body (Figure 7). At the runoff origin, collect half of the soil sample (equivalent to 2.5 mL) and deposit it into a 50 mL Falcon tube. Proceed along the runoff path, collecting additional soil at various points to accumulate a total of 5 mL of soil in the tube. Following soil collection, add 5 mL of AVL buffer to the tube (Figure 8). Avoid collecting soil in close proximity to the water body. It is advisable to remove the top layer of soil (approximately half a centimeter) before sampling to limit UV-degradation of eDNAs.

Continue along the runoff path until reaching the water body, either lentic or lotic. Collect 2 replicated water samples using high-capacity Waterra capsule filters (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Run-off path identification. Yellow points suggest possible soil sampling points and Blue points suggest water sampling point.

Figure 8 Soil sample collection and preservation procedure.

Assemble the tubes, pump, and batteries as depicted in figure 9.a, place the filter inlet in the water and initiate the filtering process (see Figure 5.b). If sampling from a lotic water source, progress upstream during filtration to prevent cross-contamination. b. To measure the volume filtered, either use a graduated container to collect the water discharged by the pump or

record the duration of pumping if the pump's discharge rate is established. c. Continue filtering until reaching the target volume of 20 liters.

Figure 9. Water sample filtration and preservation

Once filtration is complete, insert 25 ml of AVL buffer in the filter. To optimize DNA preservation, apply the buffer at both ends of the water capsule as shown in figure 9c. Both water samples (in capsule filters) and soil samples (in 50 mL Falcon tubes) can be stored at room temperature following the addition of AVL buffer.

2.5 DNA extraction from environmental samples

RNA/DNAase-free water was added to the falcon tubes containing samples from filtered water or soil, to reach a final volume of 50 mL, followed by centrifugation (20 min at 16000g). The supernatant was discarded, and 250 mg of sediment content was transferred into PowerBead Pro tubes. eDNA was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen GmbH, Hilden, Germany). Negative controls were included in the extraction procedure.

2.6 Metabarcoding sequencing

2.6.1 Library Preparation and Miseq Sequencing

DNA was then amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), including blanks, focusing on two molecular regions: the 12S rRNA V5-loop using the primer set 12S-V5 (Riaz et al., 2011) and the 16S rRNA gene using the primer set V16S-U (Wang et al., 2021). All primers contained Illumina overhang adaptors at the 5' end. PCR reactions were performed by mixing 7.5 µL QIAGEN Multiplex PCR Master Mix, 4.2 µL ultrapure water, 0.4 µL of each primer and 2.5 µL DNA extract. Cycling conditions consisted of an initial denaturation at 95°C for 15 min, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 s, annealing at 49°C for 30 s for 12S and 50°C for 25s for 16S, and extension at 72°C for 15 s, with a final extension cycle at 60°C for 10 min. For each sample, two PCR replicates were obtained. Amplification success was confirmed by visual inspection of 2 µl of each PCR product on a 2% agarose gel. A second PCR was carried out, to attach the unique dual P5 and P7 indexes, in volumes of 10 µl, comprising 5 µl 2 × KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix (Kapa Biosystems, Cape Town, South Africa), 1 µl of mixed indexing primer (5 µM stock), 2 µl ultrapure water and 2 µl of diluted first-round PCR product. Cycling conditions consisted of an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 3 min, followed by 10 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s, 55 °C for 30 s and 72 °C for 30 s, with an extension of 72 °C for 5 min. Indexing PCR success was also evaluated through agarose gel. PCR products were purified using 1.2 × AMPure® XP beads, quantified with Epoch (Biotec, USA) and diluted. These sample libraries were then pooled per marker and quantified using qPCR (KAPA Library Quantification Kit for Illumina platforms) to obtain a final pool normalized to 4 nM. The final library was sequenced in an Illumina MiSeq System using a MiSeq V3 600-cycle reagent kit (Illumina, California, USA) with an expected average of 50,000 paired-end reads per replicate.

2.6.2 Bioinformatic filtering and taxonomic assignment

The obtained sequences were bioinformatically processed using the OBITools software (Boyer et al., 2016). Paired-end reads were first aligned using the `illuminapairedend` command and discarded if the overlap quality was less than 40. Unaligned sequences were also removed using the `obigprep` command. Sequences were then dereplicated to unique sequences per sample using `obiuniq`, and primer sequences were removed using `ngsfilter`. Sequence lengths were trimmed to the expected mean length of 100 bp for 12S and 250 bp for 16S, and sequences with less than two reads were removed. A clustering analysis was performed using `sumaccluster` with 97% similarity between sequences to remove PCR and sequencing errors. To remove potential residual errors, post-clustering curation was performed in R software v4.4.2 (R Core team, 2024) using the LULU package (Frøslev et al., 2017) with a minimum similarity threshold of 84%. Read counts from the two PCR replicates for each sample were summed, and the `decon` function of the `microDecon` package (McKnight et al., 2019) was used to remove contaminant reads based on extraction and PCR blank counts. The resulting Molecular Operational Taxonomic Units (MOTUs) were compared to the NCBI core nucleotide database using the BLAST+ software v2.16 (Camacho et al., 2009) and classified to the lowest possible taxonomic rank. Only query coverage above 91% was considered, MOTUs were identified to species level when identity percentages were at least 98%, genus \geq 95%, family \geq 92%, and order or lower taxonomic levels with percentages below 92%.

2.6.3 Data analysis

To obtain the percentage of relative read abundance (RRA) per primer, the number of reads for each taxon in a sample was divided by the total number of reads in that sample and multiplied by 100 (Deagle et al., 2019). Data from the two replicates and presence-absence data from the two primers were merged to calculate the frequency of occurrence (FO, i.e. the number of samples containing DNA of each taxon divided by the total number of samples) was calculated per taxa. Rarefaction curves were used to compare taxa richness among molecular markers (12S and 16S), environmental sample types (soil and water) and sampling strategies (control and wildlife). Richness values were estimated for the double of species with the lower sample size and differences were considered significant if the 95% confidence intervals did not overlap (Chao et al., 2020). The functions `iNEXT` and `ggiNEXT` from the `iNEXT` package (Hsieh et al., 2022) were used to perform and visualize this analysis, respectively. Taxa composition was compared between markers, environmental sample types and sampling selection strategies using `PERMANOVA` with the function `adonis` from `vegan` and a Jaccard distance matrix constructed with the function `vegdist`, both from the `Vegan` package (Oksanen et al., n.d.). To ensure that significant differences between species were not due to differences in variance, a beta dispersion test was performed using `betadisper` from `Vegan`. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) was used to evaluate taxa composition differences among markers, environmental sample types and sampling selection strategies. Samples were ordinated in a two-dimensional space according to diet dissimilarity, using the function `metaMDS` from the `vegan` package and based on a Jaccard distance matrix.

2.7 Nanopore sequencing

2.7.1 Library Preparation and Nanopore Sequencing

Approximately 200 ng eDNA from each sample was prepared in a final volume of 10 µL. Library preparation of samples was performed using Oxford Nanopore Technologies' Native Barcoding Kit 24 V14 for genomic DNA (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, UK). Extraction and sequencing negative controls were included in the sequencing experiment to control for sequencing contamination. The sequencing experiment was run on a R10.4.1 flowcell for 48 hours using a MinION device. We used Dorado v0.7.2 (`dna_r10.4.1_e8.2_400bps_hac@v4.3.0`) for Super high-accuracy (HAC) base-calling of all environmental samples and negative controls. The DNA control strand was removed from raw fastq files using `NanoLyse v1.2.1`. Sequencing adapters and barcodes were removed using `Porechop v0.2.4`, and the reads were filtered at a minimum quality score of 15 and minimum length of 100 bases using `Nanofilt v2.7.1`.

2.7.2 Taxonomy assignment and data curation

In order to increase the number of identified taxa, taxonomic classification of sequencing reads were performed using `kraken2` considering NCBI's `core-nt` as reference

database(database downloaded 22.01.2025). The core nucleotide database (core_nt) is an alternative to the default nucleotide (nt) database, offering better-defined content while being less than half the size, making it more computationally efficient. There is no consensus on the level of confidence score for taxonomy classification with kraken2 and most previous studies used a default score of zero and some recent studies such as Ring et al. applied a more stringent score of 0.05 (Ring et al., 2023). Therefore we decided to consider a 0.05 confidence score to increase the precision of classification by Kraken2. In both classification datasets, using TaxonKit (v0.18.01)(Shen & Ren, 2021), all assigned TaxIDs were reformatted to an eight-level list from Kingdom to Strain and were added to the datasets for downstream analyses.

2.7.3 Preparation of screening list

A list of species and their respective TaxIDs, was prepared to screen the results of native sequencing and facilitate interpretation of results. In the list we included the species present in *i.* the Eukaryotic Pathogen, Vector and Host Informatics Resource Database (VEuPathDB)(Amos et al., 2022), a collection of eukaryotic pathogens of animals and plants, arthropod vectors of medical, veterinary (and agronomic importance) and epidemiologically relevant hosts (vertebrate) for the included pathogens *ii.* a subset of the 50 priority pathogens, selected by Health working group of EFSA for environmental detection and published by the ENETWILD consortium (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2023), the subset includes only DNA-based pathogens as all RNA pathogens can not be detected with the analytical pathway chosen for this study. This list (Supplementary file Slist.csv), including approximately 700 species, was finally used to screen a dataset containing taxonomy-assigned reads using the software kraken2 (Wood et al., 2019) following the analytic pipeline proposed by Varzandi et al. (2025).

2.7.4 Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed on a subset of data that were normalized based on the initial sample amount collected in the field. Since the soil samples contained the same amount of material at sampling, only water samples were normalized, with reads downsampled to per liter of filtered water at sampling. Filtration of species belonging to the screening list was applied only to the original, non-downsampled data. All analyses were conducted in *R* using the *vegan* and *ggplot2* packages.

3 Results

3.1 eDNA Metabarcoding

All 30 water samples were successfully amplified for both markers, while all 30 soil samples were amplified for the 16S gene and 27 for the 12S gene. Following bioinformatic filtering, the mean number of reads per replicate for water samples was 33,000 for 16S and 36,000 for 12S, whereas for soil samples, it was 18,000 for 16S and 41,000 for 12S. The overall

dataset contains a total of 935 MOTUs corresponding to 816 taxa (Table S2) across 10 kingdoms, 24 phyla, 47 classes, 83 orders, 122 families, and 100 genera. The 16S marker amplified taxa from 10 kingdoms, including bacteria, fungi, plants, and vertebrates, while the 12S marker predominantly amplified vertebrate taxa (Figure S1).

In metazoans, the combination of the two markers identified 74 taxa from three phyla, seven classes, 25 orders, 57 genera and 64 species. Approximately 38% of the identified taxa were found in both molecular markers; however, 25% and 35% were identified exclusively by the 12S and 16S markers, respectively (Figure 10A), indicating marker complementarity. Rarefaction curves (Figure 10B) further support this pattern by showing a similar overall taxonomic richness of metazoans for both markers, with no significant differences indicated by the overlap of confidence intervals.

Figure 10. Comparison of Metazoan taxonomic richness detected using different molecular markers. (A) Venn diagrams illustrating the proportion of taxa detected using 12S (purple) and 16S (yellow) markers. Numbers indicate taxa uniquely detected by each marker and those shared by both. Percentages represent the frequency of occurrence of taxa detected in each category. (B) Rarefaction curves comparing taxonomic richness between 12S (purple) and 16S (yellow) markers. Solid and dashed lines represent observed and rarefied richness values, respectively. Shaded regions indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Soil and water samples provided complementary results, with approximately 23% of Metazoan taxa present in both sample types, and 15% and 63% identified exclusively in soil and water samples, respectively (Figure 11A). Similarly, the rarefaction curves (Figure 11B) show significantly higher taxa richness in water samples than soil, as indicated by the lack of overlap in the confidence intervals. These differences are associated with aquatic taxa in water samples, such as fish and amphibians, which are virtually absent in soil samples (Figure 11C and S2). When considering only terrestrial vertebrates (mammals and birds) there are no significant differences in richness between soil and water samples (Figure 11D).

Figure 11. Comparison of Metazoan taxonomic richness detected using different environmental sample types. (A) Venn diagrams illustrating the proportion of all Metazoan taxa detected in soil (brown) and water (blue) samples. Numbers indicate taxa uniquely detected by each sample type and those shared by both. Percentages represent the frequency of occurrence of taxa detected in each category. (B) Rarefaction curves comparing taxonomic richness between soil (brown) and water (blue) samples. Solid and dashed lines represent observed and rarefied richness values, respectively. Shaded regions indicate 95% confidence intervals. (C) Stacked bar plot illustrating the proportional frequency of occurrence (FO) of taxa identified in soil and water samples, categorized by taxonomic class. (D) Rarefaction curves comparing taxonomic richness of target species (mammals and birds) between soil (brown) and water (blue) samples. Solid and dashed lines represent observed and rarefied richness values, respectively. Shaded regions indicate 95% confidence intervals.

3.1.1 eDNA vs. Direct observation

Overall, eDNA from combined water and soil samples provided broader species detection than direct observation (Camera-trapping data from EOW 2023 campaign) (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2024) alone for the three countries sampled (Figures 12 and 13). Portugal showed the highest overall species richness across all methods, with 18 species detected in soil and 37 in

water (Figures 12A). Croatia and Spain presented 16 and 9 species in soil and 26 and 22 in water, respectively (Figures 12A). A total of 11 species were identified across the sampling methods, however, 32 species were identified exclusively with direct observations, 33 with water sampling and 2 with soil sampling (Figure 12B).

Figure 12. Comparison of Metazoan species detected using different sampling strategies. (A) Number of detected species for each country (Croatia, Portugal, and Spain) using three different sampling methods: direct observation (green), soil eDNA (brown), water eDNA (blue), and total (soil and water) eDNA (gray). (B) Venn diagrams illustrating the proportion of taxa detected using direct observation (green), soil eDNA (brown) and water eDNA (blue). Numbers indicate taxa uniquely detected by each marker/sample type and those shared by both.

The classes Actinopteri, Amphibia, Hydrozoa, and Reptilia were detected only in eDNA from water samples (Figure 13). All these species are exclusively aquatic (Actinopteri and Hydrozoa) or strictly related to aquatic environments (Amphibia and Reptilia- *Mauremys leprosa* Iberian Pond Turtle). Birds and mammals were detected through both direct observation and eDNA sampling. Eleven species were detected in both sample types (i.e. water and soil): 3 birds (*Columba palumbus*, *Sylvia atricapilla* and *Turdus philomelos*), one rodent (*A. sylvaticus*), 3 domestic species (*Bos taurus*, *Canis lupus familiaris* and *Ovis aries*), 2 deers (*C. capreolus* and *C. elaphus*) and *S. scrofa* which with eDNA was not possible to distinguish wild or domestic. Wolf (*C. lupus*) is known to be present in two of the study areas (namely, Portugal and Croatia), in Portugal *C. lupus signatus* is reported. The barcodes used for the current analysis cannot differentiate at subspecies level, thus the reads of *C. lupus* can be attributed to both dog and wolf. In mammals, direct observation identified 36 species, while eDNA metabarcoding resulted in detection of 41 species across all countries with 16 species revealed in soil and 25 revealed in water samples (Figure 13). By combining all sampling methods, a broader representation of species composition can be achieved, totaling to 46 mammal species. Per country, direct observation identified 26, 23, and 11 mammal species, while soil sampling identified 11, 12, and 5 species, and water sampling identified 18, 13, and 11 species for Croatia, Portugal, and Spain, respectively (Figure 13). This totals

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35, 28, and 17 mammal species for Croatia, Portugal, and Spain, respectively, when combining all sampling methods (direct observations, soil, and water eDNA).

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Figure 13 (on top). Heatmap depicting the presence of each species, ordered by class, across countries (Croatia, Portugal and Spain) and sampling methods (directed observation - green, soil eDNA - brown and water eDNA - blue).

3.1.2 Sampling site selection approaches (control and wildlife)

When considering all countries collectively, there were significant differences in taxa richness between the two sampling site selection approaches (control and wildlife; Figure 14A). This difference is mainly influenced by samples from Portuguese study area, while in Croatia and Spain taxa richness are comparable between wildlife and control points (Figure S3). Control samples exhibited higher species richness values compared to sites chosen for wildlife. This pattern was similar in Portugal; however, for Croatia and Spain, no differences in species richness were observed between control and wildlife sites (Figure S3). When considering only terrestrial vertebrates (mammals and birds) there are no significant differences in richness between control and wildlife samples (Figure 14C). There were no differences in species composition between control and wildlife sites both considering all Metazoans identified and only mammals and birds (Figure 14B and 14D).

Figure 14. Comparison of Metazoan taxa detection between different sampling site selection approaches (control and wildlife) for all countries. (A) Rarefaction curves comparing taxonomic richness between control (red) and wildlife (yellow) points. Solid and dashed lines

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represent observed and rarefied richness values, respectively. Shaded regions indicate 95% confidence intervals. (B) Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of taxonomic composition detected across the two sampling site selection approaches. Each point represents a sample, colored by sampling site selection approaches (control in red and wildlife in yellow), with ellipses indicating the variation within each group. (C) Rarefaction curves comparing taxonomic richness of target species (mammals and birds) between control (red) and wildlife (yellow) points. (D) NMDS of the composition of mammals and birds detected across the two sampling site selection approaches.

3.1.3 Community composition across countries

Overall, *Homo sapiens* had the highest frequency of occurrence (FO), appearing in all samples of the three countries. It was followed by *S. scrofa* unknown (unk- not possible to distinguish wild or domestic) with 87% frequency, *C. lupus familiaris* with 80%, *O. aries* with 70%, and *C. elaphus* with 60% (Figure 15A). Croatia also exhibited *C. lupus familiaris* (FO = 90%), *S. scrofa* unk (FO = 80%), *O. aries* (FO = 70%), and *T. philomelos* (FO = 60%) as the most frequent. In Portugal, the most frequently detected species also included *O. aries* (FO = 90%), *C. lupus familiaris* (FO = 80%), *S. scrofa* unk (FO = 80%), *C. elaphus* (FO = 70%), and *A. sylvaticus* (FO = 60%). Spain presented *C. elaphus* and *S. scrofa* unk as the most frequently occurring taxa occurring in 100% of the samples, followed by *Galemys pyrenaicus* and *C. lupus familiaris* with a frequency of 70%. The NMDS shows differences in species composition among countries (Figure 15B).

Figure 15. Composition of Metazoan taxa across countries. (A) Frequency of occurrence of detected vertebrate taxa across three study sites (Croatia, Portugal, and Spain). Colors indicate different countries: red for Croatia, green for Portugal, and blue for Spain. (B) Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of species composition detected across the three countries.

On average, 10 taxa (species + genera) were recorded per sampling site, with country-specific means of 10 taxa in Croatia, 13 in Portugal and 8 in Spain. Among vertebrates, the mean number of taxa per site was 3 for fish, 1 for amphibians, 2 for birds and 6 for mammals.

Hydroid species (Hydrozoa) were consistently found with an average of 1 taxon per site. Reptiles were found at only one sampling site, PT8.07 from Portugal, highlighting their limited detectability in this study. The points with the highest richness were both in Portugal (PT9.08 with 29 and PT8.07 with 27 taxa), while the points with the lowest richness were Sp-10 in Croatia and QM-B8 in Spain, both with 5 taxa detected (Figure 16 and Figure S5).

Figure 16. Taxa richness across sampling points within each country divided by class.

Overall, *Homo sapiens* (RRA = 33%), *Cervus elaphus* (RRA = 15%), and *Sus scrofa* (RRA = 10%) had the highest relative read abundance values. In Croatia and Portugal, the highest RRA values corresponded to *Homo sapiens* (RRA = 33% and 44%, respectively) and *Sus scrofa* (RRA = 12% and 11%, respectively). In Spain, the highest RRA corresponded to *Cervus elaphus* (RRA = 53%) and *Homo sapiens* (RRA = 13%). A positive correlation (Figure 17A) existed between density and relative read abundance for the three species we had information on for both sampling methods (*Sus scrofa*, *Capreolus capreolus* and *Vulpes vulpes*) in the three countries. This pattern was similar for the three countries individually (Figure 17B-D). However, this correlation was not significant (Figure 17; most likely due to the reduced number of samples).

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Figure 17. Correlation between log-transformed estimated observed density and relative read abundance for species with data available from both methodologies (direct observation and metabarcoding). (A) Correlation considering all countries together and separately in (B) Croatia, (C) Portugal and (D) Spain. Pearson correlation coefficient (R) values and significance values (p) are shown in all graphs.

Alternatively, we subscaled analyses at the Trap Chamber Level comparing relative abundances derived from the camera trapping index (direct observation) with metabarcoding data obtained from water samples. For some species, such as wild boar and red deer, a positive correlation between the two methodologies was observed. However, this correlation was statistically significant only for red deer (see Figure 18 B).

Figure 18. Comparison of Capture Rates and Normalized Sequence Counts by species (water samples). Only water samples and locations with available data from both methodologies were included in analysis.

Comparison between the capture rates from camera traps (located near water sampling points) and the normalized counts of sequences recorded for each species. Only locations with available data from both methodologies are shown.

3.2 Native sequencing

Nanopore native sequencing generated a total of 13,739,033 sequencing reads, with mean and median read lengths of 3,845 and 1,851, respectively. The Nanopore quality score averaged 18.7 with a median of 19.8. Approximately 25% (3,483,428) of reads were successfully mapped to references in the core_nt database using the Kraken2 classifier. Taxonomic classification of the sequencing reads identified 12,228 taxa across different taxonomic levels of the tree of life, with 9,453 assigned at the species level. The majority of identified taxa were prokaryotic. As shown in Figure 19, only a small proportion of the top 20 most abundant taxa, which account for nearly 70% of the classified reads, were assigned to eukaryotes.

Figure 19. Top 20 taxa identified with Kraken2 for nanopore native sequencing reads. The identified taxa belong to different taxonomic levels (d for domain, k for kingdom, p for phylum, o for order, c for class, f for family, g for genus and s for species).

Almost half (48.2%) of the identified species were present in both water and soil samples. However, the proportion of species found exclusively in water samples (32.3%) was higher than that of species identified solely in soil samples (19.5%) (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. Distribution of identified species with nanopore native sequencing across different sample types for all samples analyzed in this study.

Among identified taxa, a range comprised between 24 and 41% were identified both in water and soil samples in all three different countries (Fig. 21)

Figure 21. Number of identified species with nanopore native sequencing in water and/or soil samples in the three study areas (% of total species identified).

The diversity of the all identified taxa was slightly higher in samples collected from wildlife areas only in Croatia and control areas in Portugal and Spain showed higher diversity, however the difference seen was not statistically significant when tested with Kruskal-Wallis Test for Shannon Index (p-value = 0.56)(Fig 22a).

Our read-mapping approach identified 86 vertebrate taxa, 46 of which were assigned at the species level with the majority of them belonging to low-abundance reads. As expected with native sequencing the absolute majority of sequenced reads belongs to the highly abundant microbiome proper of soil and water. We investigated the diversity of these taxa between two sampling areas: a Wildlife area (high WTR) and a Control area (low WTR) (Fig. 22 b). Diversity of vertebrate taxa (mammals and birds only), measured using the Shannon index, was higher in the Wildlife area compared to the Control area in Croatia and Portugal, but not in Spain. However, these differences were not statistically significant when tested with Kruskal-Wallis Test for Shannon Index(p-value = 0.82).

Figure 22. Taxa diversity (Shannon index) resulting from native sequencing is compared for points classified as having high WTR (wildlife) and for sampling points classified as having low WTR (control). In panel a. the overall diversity is shown, while in panel b. the taxa diversity related only to terrestrial mammals (only species detectable by direct observation and thus contributing to a priori-site selection).

The number of terrestrial vertebrate species identified with Nanopore native sequencing is lower compared to metabarcoding, nevertheless the two approaches do complement each other (Fig. 23). One instance is the identification of some Chiroptera species like *Pipistrellus kuhli* and *Hypsugo alaschanicus*. These species were identified via native sequencing but not with metabarcoding.

Figure 23. Vertebrate species (Mammalia and Aves) identified at species level via native sequencing. Entries identified at higher taxonomic level (i.e. at Genus level) are not shown.

After filtering our classification results using the species listed in the screening list (Supplementary File Slist.csv), we identified 87 species of relevance for disease monitoring. Results from native sequencing combined with such a screening approach enabled us to identify potential pathogens, hosts and vectors belonging to distinct domains of the tree of life all at once. Based on our results, the majority of identified species belong to eukaryotic pathogens among them fungi causing diseases in plants seemed prevalent. For instance, *Fusarium* species are among important plant pathogens and causative agents of invasive fusariosis, affecting immunocompetent and, more frequently, immunocompromised patients. Moreover, native sequencing approach enabled us to identify possible and important

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arthropod and gastropod vectors that are responsible for maintenance of various diseases (known or unknown in the studied areas). Identified species mainly belong to *Anopheles*, *Aedes*, *Culex* and *Biomphalaria* genera. These species alongside identified pathogens (Tab. 3) can be considered as potential candidates for further active surveillance using targeted molecular methods. The distribution of these species in relation to their sampling point area (Wildlife area (high WTR) and a Control area (low WTR)) is presented in Figures 24, 25, and 26 for Spain, Portugal, and Croatia, respectively.

Country	Species	Role	Distribution status	References
Spain, Croatia	<i>Anopheles darlingi</i>	Relevant vector of malaria in South America.	Not known to be present in study area	
Spain	<i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i>		Endemic in cattle in Spain and previously reported in immediate surroundings of the study area. Cattle was also detected in the study area as are present in immediate surrounding farms.	Gutiérrez-Expósito, D., Ortega-Mora, Luis. M., Marco, I., Boadella, M., Gortázar, C., San Miguel-Ayanz, J. M., García-Lunar, P., Lavín, S., & Álvarez-García, G. (2013). First serosurvey of <i>Besnoitia</i> spp. Infection in wild European ruminants in Spain. <i>Veterinary Parasitology</i> , 197(3), 557–564. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2013.05.017 B.1.
Spain, Portugal, Croatia	<i>Eimeria tenella</i>	Intestinal Coccidia of Gallus gallus	Ubiquitous world wide	
Spain, Portugal, Croatia	<i>Phlebotomus papatasi</i>	Vector of <i>Leishmania infantum</i> and Arboviruses including Toscana Virus	Present across Spain, reported in Souther Portugal	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/
Spain	<i>Phlebotomus argentipes</i>	Primary vector for cutaneous and visceral leishmaniasis in Asia	Not reported in Europe	
Spain, Portugal	<i>Rhipicephalus sanguineus</i>	Competent vector of pathogens belonging to the genera Babesia, Hepatozoon, Anaplasma, Rickettsia, Mycoplasma, Theileria, Coxiella	Reported in study area	
Spain	<i>Stomoxys calcitrans</i>	Hematophagous fly of domestic and wild ruminants, important vector of bacterial, viral and parasitic pathogens	Ubiquitous world wide	Moraga-Fernández, A., Ruiz-Fons, F., Habela, M. A., Royo-Hernández, L., Calero-Bernal, R., Gortazar, C., de la Fuente, J., & Fernández de Mera, I. G. (2021). Detection of new

				Crimean–Congo haemorrhagic fever virus genotypes in ticks feeding on deer and wild boar, Spain. <i>Transboundary and Emerging Diseases</i> , 68(3), 993–1000. https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.13756
Portugal	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	Invasive species, important vectors of pathogens including Yellow Fever Virus, Dengue Fever Virus, and Chikungunya Virus, as well as several filarial nematodes such as <i>Dirofilaria immitis</i> .	Invasive in the study area	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/
Portugal	<i>Anopheles sp.</i>	Arthropod vector of Plasmodium spp.	Several species of the genus Anopheles are known to be present in the study area	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/
Portugal, Croatia	<i>Culex quinquefasciatus</i>	Belonging to the Culex pipiens complex	Vector of filarial parasites such as filarial parasites and West Nile Virus	Vogels, C. B. F., Fros, J. J., Göertz, G. P., Pijlman, G. P., & Koenraadt, C. J. M. (2016). Vector competence of northern European Culex pipiens biotypes and hybrids for West Nile virus is differentially affected by temperature. <i>Parasites & Vectors</i> , 9(1), 393. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-016-1677-0
Portugal	<i>Leishmania donovani</i>	Complex of different species causing visceral leishmanias	Present in the area	Fernández-Arévalo, A., El Baidouri, F., Ravel, C., Ballart, C., Abras, A., Lachaud, L., Tebar, S., Lami, P., Pratlong, F., Gállego, M., & Muñoz, C. (2020). The <i>Leishmania donovani</i> species complex: A new insight into taxonomy☆. <i>International Journal for Parasitology</i> , 50(13), 1079–1088. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2020.06.013
Portugal	<i>Negleria fowleri</i>	Aethiological agent of Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis (PAM)	PAM cases reported in Spain and several European Countries	Maciver, S. K., Piñero, J. E., & Lorenzo-Morales, J. (2020). Is Naegleria fowleri an Emerging Parasite? <i>Trends in Parasitology</i> , 36(1), 19–28. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2019.10.008
Portugal	<i>Yersinia pestis</i>	Causative agent of human plague	Not reported in Western Europe, closest endemic foci in Algeria and Lybia	Mas Fiol, G., Demeure, C., Guern, A.-S. L., & Pizarro-Cerdá, J. (2023). <i>Yersinia pestis</i> and plague in the 21st century: Learning from a

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				distant past. <i>The Biochemist</i> , 45(2), 1–5. https://doi.org/10.1042/bio_2023_109
Croatia	<i>Leishmania sp.</i>	Genus including causative agents of Human, canine cutaneous and Visceral Leishmaniasis	Present in the area	Fernández-Arévalo, A., El Baidouri, F., Ravel, C., Ballart, C., Abras, A., Lachaud, L., Tebar, S., Lami, P., Pratlong, F., Gállego, M., & Muñoz, C. (2020). The <i>Leishmania donovani</i> species complex: A new insight into taxonomy☆. <i>International Journal for Parasitology</i> , 50(13), 1079–1088. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2020.06.013
Croatia	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	Causative agent of Toxoplasmosis, known to infect a wide range of warm-blooded species	Present in the area	Fernández-Escobar, M., Schares, G., Maksimov, P., Joeres, M., Ortega-Mora, L. M., & Calero-Bernal, R. (2022). Toxoplasma gondii Genotyping: A Closer Look Into Europe. <i>Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology</i> , 12. https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.842595
Croatia	<i>Trypanosoma theileri</i>	Non-pathogenic bovine parasite transmitted by tabanid flies	Present in the area	Oldrieve, G. R., Malacart, B., López-Vidal, J., & Matthews, K. R. (2022). The genomic basis of host and vector specificity in non-pathogenic trypanosomatids. <i>Biology Open</i> , 11(4), bio059237. https://doi.org/10.1242/bio.059237

Table 3: Potential pathogens and vector candidates for active surveillance

eDNA and Integrated surveillance

Figure 24. Subset of identified species after filtering for those present in the screening list (including potential eukaryotic or prokaryotic pathogens, vectors, and hosts for further surveillance) and their association with different wildlife areas (high WTR) or control areas (low WTR) in Spain.

eDNA and Integrated surveillance

Figure 25. Subset of identified species after filtering for those present in the screening list (including potential eukaryotic or prokaryotic pathogens, vectors, and hosts for further surveillance) and their association with different wildlife areas (high WTR) or control areas (low WTR) in Portugal.

eDNA and Integrated surveillance

Figure 26. Subset of identified species after filtering for those present in the screening list (including potential eukaryotic or prokaryotic pathogens, vectors, and hosts for further surveillance) and their association with different wildlife areas (high WTR) or control areas (low WTR) in Croatia.

4 Discussion

Molecular techniques have long become essential in the fields of ecology and biodiversity sciences. Approximately ten years ago, the advent of eDNA analysis introduced remarkable novelty into biodiversity research. The use of eDNA involves detecting biodiversity indicators from intracellular and extracellular DNA recovered from environmental samples. The use of eDNA has evolved over time from studying population dynamics of single species, to identifying previously undocumented biodiversity (i.e. cryptic species, invasive and alien species) both well-examined and lesser-known ecosystems. It has evolved from being a strictly ecological/biological tool to being a valuable tool in health-related fields of research,

including disease surveillance, contamination assessment and evolutionary biology (ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2022; ENETWILD-consortium et al., 2023). Today, only a limited number of surveillance systems include environment-derived samples as matrix for pathogen surveillance. In the recently established HaDEA One Health Surveillance Grant funded by the EU Commission, 7 targeted priority pathogens include surveillance activities via environmental sampling. These 7 pathogens are mainly vector-borne (*Borrelia burgdorferi* s.l., *Coxiella burnetii*, Crimean-Congo Haemorrhagic Fever Virus, Tick-borne encephalitis Virus, West Nile Fever Virus) or transmissible via direct contact or contact with fomites (Highly pathogenic Avian Influenza Virus and Swine Influenza type A Virus). All these surveillance efforts are targeted for a specific pathogen/host/environment. One of the key advantages of eDNA-based monitoring is its capacity for passive surveillance. This approach is especially useful for early detection of pathogens and host/vector species in areas previously considered disease-free. It also allows for the monitoring of intervention outcomes on pathogens and hosts, or for confirming the absence of specific diseases. Surveillance based on environmental samples can benefit from the combined use of different types of matrices to detect pathogens (such as water and biological materials, soil or air). A particularly valuable feature of eDNA-based surveillance is its intrinsic integrated nature where integrated here refers specifically to integrated wildlife Health Monitoring as defined by Cardoso et al. (2022). Particularly with metagenomic approaches, the possibility of simultaneously detecting hosts, vectors and pathogens is very concrete. Yet fundamental research is needed to apply environmental surveillance within structured pathogen surveillance systems. A concrete step toward practical application of a multi-targeted or passive eDNA-based surveillance is to develop standardized and harmonized methods for sample collection. As reported in a recent paper by Blackman et al. (2024), the research effort in trying to evaluate, test and improve sampling strategies represents a limited proportion of the available literature on eDNA and it has not grown over time despite the huge growth of research literature in the field. The present report represents a pilot study aimed at verifying multiple objectives: *i.* if camera trap (direct observation) occurrence data (WTR and LTR) can be used as meaningful priors to inform sampling site selection, *ii.* to verify the performance of metabarcoding coupled with metagenomic approaches toward an integrated approach to wildlife related pathogens surveillance and to *iii.* make progress on harmonized and replicable strategy for the identification of sampling sites to maximize sensitivity.

As expected, metabarcoding proved to be more sensitive and specific in identifying vertebrate biodiversity compared to metagenomics. Metabarcoding results highlighted the importance of marker selection when designing biodiversity assessments using eDNA. The comparison of 12S and 16S showed that while both markers identified overlapping taxa, each also identified unique species, highlighting that the use of a multi-marker approach improves the detection of biodiversity by capturing taxa that may be missed when using a single marker (Adamowicz et al., 2019). The 16S marker captured greater diversity, consistent with previous research showing that 16S often detects a wider range of taxa, particularly bacteria and certain eukaryotic groups, whereas 12S is more focused on vertebrates (Othman et al., 2021). Furthermore, the integration of different environmental samples (water and soil) improved the detected biodiversity. Water samples yield greater species richness than soil, mainly related to aquatic species, but soil still provides uniquely detected taxa, highlighting the benefits of multi-habitat sampling for more complete biodiversity surveys. In addition, our results highlight the complementarity of eDNA and direct observation via camera trapping in characterising vertebrate communities. While both methods provide valuable insights, they detect overlapping but distinct subsets of the community, highlighting the importance of integrating multiple approaches for biodiversity assessments. When considering only terrestrial vertebrates, our results (detected species through eDNA metabarcoding) showed

no significant differences in community composition between control and wildlife-selected sites based on direct observation (camera trap occurrence) data. In addition, the potential positive correlation between density estimates from direct observation via camera traps and relative abundance values from metabarcoding reads, although not statistically significant - probably due to the limited amount of data - suggests that eDNA can provide semi-quantitative insights into species abundance, consistent with previous research showing a relationship between RRA and population density (e.g. Di Muri et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021). However, the results may be influenced by several factors, including the limited number of stations providing both types of data, the inability to distinguish between wild and domestic variants of wild boar, and the type of water source used in each region. These limitations suggest that further standardisation is needed. An example highlighting the complementary role of eDNA methods is the detection of a large number of rodent species (primarily through metabarcoding and also with nanopore native sequencing), which are typically beyond the scope of current camera-trapping protocols. Additionally, our results demonstrated the capacity of metabarcoding to detect invasive species, such as the American mink, as well as unexpected species, such as *Galemys pyrenaicus*, which is not known to inhabit the sampling area. The detection of *G. pyrenaicus* in the Quintos de Mora study area could represent an early signal of this species' biogeographical expansion or the presence of cryptic populations. However, this interpretation should be approached cautiously and requires further validation, as false-positive detections may occur due to factors such as molecular method sensitivity, specificity, and limitations in genomic databases. The fact that results from environmental surveillance should be taken cautiously, at least at this early stage of prospective integration into systematic surveillance systems, is true on a very general level. For metabarcoding as well as for metagenomics, results should be always verified via targeted surveillance. It is indeed in the very nature of these methods to serve as an indication and a warning signal for early detection. Another notable finding in our study is the detection of human, domestic, and wild animal DNA, highlighting the broad taxonomic coverage of eDNA. The presence of human DNA is a recurrent issue in metabarcoding studies and may originate from direct contamination during sampling or reflect actual human presence in the environment (Zhan, 2025). In this study, during field sampling all precautions were taken to minimize the risk of human contamination as well as in the laboratory where human contamination was highly controlled, with extraction and PCR blanks used as controls to detect and remove any potential contamination. Human reads present in these blanks were excluded during the filtering process, ensuring that our results reflect true environmental DNA rather than laboratory contamination. Consequently, the detection of human DNA in our filtered dataset is likely to represent its actual presence in the sampled environment, highlighting the widespread influence of human activity in eDNA studies. The detection of domestic species, including cattle and dogs, demonstrates how eDNA reflects anthropogenic influences on ecosystems. Due to their higher abundance, their DNA is likely to be deposited more frequently and abundantly at sampling sites, which can influence the detectability of target species in eDNA biodiversity surveys. Metabarcoding results highlight the importance of integrating eDNA with other survey techniques to provide a more comprehensive assessment of biodiversity. While eDNA is a powerful tool for detecting species presence across broad taxonomic groups, its limitations highlight the need for methodological refinement and careful interpretation of results. The combination of eDNA and camera trapping provides a more holistic approach to monitor wildlife communities, particularly in systems where species detection is difficult due to behavioural, ecological or methodological constraints. The combination of metabarcoding with metagenomics is another example of complementarity of methods. The vast majority (95%) of nanopore native sequencing reads were assigned to prokaryotic species after mapping to NCBI's *core-nt* reference database. Despite their lower read counts compared to prokaryotic classifications, the classified reads of eukaryotes provided valuable insights into

species biodiversity across all other domains of the tree of life. Water samples accounted for a higher number of identified species than soil (Fig 20), a difference partially explained by the large number of species detected in samples from Portugal (Fig.21). A similar pattern was observed in the metabarcoding experiment, although the extent of taxonomic identification was more limited. To effectively screen the enormous amount of data originating from metagenomic analysis, we developed a screening list containing pathogens, hosts and arthropod vectors for which wildlife plays a significant epidemiological role.

Focusing on species (pathogens, vectors and vertebrate hosts) present in the screening list, *B. besnoiti*—a protozoan parasite and cyst-forming coccidia that causes protozoal disease in cattle—was identified alongside its primary domestic host, *Bos taurus*, and a potential wild host, the red deer (*Cervus elaphus*). This parasite is endemic in cattle in Spain and has previously been reported in the immediate vicinity of the study area, where cattle are farmed. Additionally, *Besnoitia* spp. infections have been documented in wild European ruminants in Spain (Gutiérrez-Expósito et al., 2013) (Fig. 24). Similarly, though of lesser significance, the ubiquitous coccidian parasite *E. tenella*—the causative agent of hemorrhagic cecal colicidiosis in poultry—was detected (in all three countries) alongside its primary host, the domestic chicken (*Gallus gallus*) which was detected in samples from Spain and Croatia (Fig. 24 and 26). Specifically regarding *E. tenella*, the results should be interpreted with caution, as the abundance of reference sequences for this parasite might skew the identification of coccidian parasites in favor of this better characterized species. Nevertheless, the significance of this detection lies in the ability of the native sequencing approach to identify both the parasite and its primary hosts using a unified method. This demonstrates promising potential, particularly for detecting parasitic diseases with complex life cycles involving multiple hosts. *P. papatasi*, a sand fly and vector of various pathogens such as *L. infantum* and Arboviruses, including Toscana virus, was detected in all three study areas. All study areas are known for the presence of this species (ECDC, 2023). However, its detection was associated with a pathogen (a member of the *Leishmania* species complex) only in the Portugal and Croatia study areas (Fig. 25 and 26). The detection of *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*—a competent vector of pathogens from the genera *Babesia*, *Hepatozoon*, *Anaplasma*, *Rickettsia*, *Mycoplasma*, *Theileria*, and *Coxiella*—in the Spanish and Portuguese study areas, as well as *Stomoxys calcitrans*—a hematophagous fly of domestic and wild ruminants and an important vector of bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens—in Spain, has been previously reported. *Aedes albopictus* was also detected. This is an invasive species and a major vector of pathogens such as Yellow Fever Virus, Dengue Fever Virus, Chikungunya Virus, and several filarial nematodes, including *D. immitis*—and *C. quinquefasciatus*—a member of the *C. pipiens* complex and a vector of filarial parasites and West Nile Virus—has also been documented in the study areas. The identification of arthropod vectors is crucial for the surveillance of vector-borne diseases. Its value is further enhanced when monitoring efforts can simultaneously detect both vectors and their associated DNA-based pathogens. Among the identified arthropod vectors, *P. argentipes*—the primary vector for cutaneous and visceral leishmaniasis in Asia (Tripathi & Nailwal, 2021)—was detected only in Spain. Additionally, *A. darlingi*, a significant malaria vector in South America, was detected in samples from Spain and Croatia (Fig. 24). However, there is no prior knowledge of its presence in these regions, as it is typically associated with distinct biogeographical areas. Nevertheless, such identification does not rule out the presence of other species within the same genus, as erroneous taxonomic assignment at the species level is more likely due to the relatively higher error rate of nanopore sequencing compared to other platforms. However, this error rate can be mitigated through more accurate base-calling configurations, though these require substantial computational resources which were behind the scope of this report but could be implemented to further approach eDNA based surveillance to systematic surveillance systems. Detection of

Naegleria fowleri - etiological agent of Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis (PAM) in water samples originated from Portugal could serve as another example of how native sequencing can lead to detection of environmentally mediated infectious species which are neglected or need particular monitoring settings for surveillance (Sokolow et al., 2022). Available literature only includes data clinical level which demonstrates an increase in PAM reported cases since 2000 among them several European countries including Spain (Maciver et al., 2020). *Yersinia pestis* remains as the only prokaryotic species identified after filtering our classified reads with the screening list. Causative agent of human plague which is not reported in the Western Europe and the closest endemic foci is reported in Algeria and Libya. At last, *Toxoplasma gondii*, detected in the Prolom study area and known to be present (Fig. 26), is the causative agent of toxoplasmosis and can infect a wide range of warm-blooded species. However, its definitive hosts are limited to domestic and wild felids. The primary transmission routes include the ingestion of tissue cysts in infected animal tissues and the consumption of oocysts from contaminated water, soil, or food. Due to the high persistence of *T. gondii* oocysts in the environment, their detection is a priority for both animal and human health (Shapiro et al., 2019).

5 Conclusions

This report concludes that while environmental DNA (eDNA) methodologies provide valuable tools for wildlife health monitoring, they require further standardization and integration into existing systematic surveillance frameworks to optimize their effectiveness. The findings from this study contribute to the refinement of integrated monitoring strategies, which are critical for the effective management of wildlife diseases. Moving forward, it is expected that wildlife disease surveillance may incorporate these technologies more extensively, given their potential to offer detailed and timely data essential for informed decision-making in public health and biodiversity conservation. However, the actual extent of reliance on and benefits from eDNA methodologies will depend on overcoming current technical and integration challenges

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7 Annexes

A– Metagenomic screening list

B– Additional graphs for metabarcoding and metagenomic analysis

C– Glossary

Annex C - Glossary

DEM: Digital Elevation Model is a representation of the bare ground (bare earth) topographic surface of the Earth excluding trees, buildings, and any other surface objects

eDNA: Environmental DNA (eDNA) refers to genetic material shed by organisms into their surrounding environment

FO: Frequency of Occurrence which informs the presence of a particular taxon (species, genus, etc.) in a set of samples.

IDW: Inverse Distance Weighting is a spatial interpolation method used to estimate the value of a variable at an unmeasured location based on the values of nearby measured points

LTR: livestock trapping rate (LTR area is defined as the area with higher livestock density)

Metabarcoding: a PCR-based molecular method used to identify multiple species within a mixed DNA sample

Metagenomics: the study of genetic material recovered directly from environmental samples, encompassing all organisms within that environment, without the need for isolating and culturing individual microbes

MOTU: sequence clusters resulted from metabarcoding experiments used in molecular biology to classify and study biodiversity

REM: Random Encounter Model estimates animal densities from camera-trap data by correcting capture rates for a set of biological variables of the animals (average group size, speed and activity level) and characteristics of camera sensors

RRA: Relative read abundance refers to the proportion of DNA sequencing reads that are assigned to a specific taxon (like a species or gene) relative to the total number of reads in a sample.

WTR: wildlife trapping rate (WTR area is defined as the area with higher wildlife density)